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Polar Lows and Their Effects on Sea Ice and the Upper Ocean in the Iceland, Greenland, and Labrador Seas

O. Gutjahr¹ **Key Points:**

- First explicit simulation of polar lows in a globally coupled climate simulation with kilometer-scale (2.5 km) resolution in all components
- Polar lows lead to considerable heat loss from the ocean near the sea ice edge and from leads and polynyas in the sea ice cover
- Polar lows are important for water mass transformation in the western Iceland and Greenland Seas, in the Labrador Sea, and within polynyas

Correspondence to:

O. Gutjahr,

oliver.gutjahr@mpimet.mpg.de**Citation:**

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Author Contributions:**Conceptualization:** O. Gutjahr, C. Mehlmann**Formal analysis:** O. Gutjahr**Methodology:** O. Gutjahr, C. Mehlmann**Visualization:** O. Gutjahr**Writing – original draft:** O. Gutjahr**Writing – review & editing:** O. Gutjahr, C. Mehlmann

Abstract Using two case studies, we analyze the effects of explicitly resolving polar lows in a global climate model (ICON-Sapphire) with a high resolution of 2.5 km on the upper ocean and sea ice. We aim to understand the mechanism of how polar lows form in a global coupled model and how they interact with the upper ocean and sea ice. When polar lows form at the sea ice edge, they induce marine cold air outbreaks that lead to large heat loss from the ocean. This heat loss contributes to dense water formation in the Iceland and Greenland Seas, which replenishes the climatically important Denmark Strait Overflow Water (DSOW). The high wind speeds of polar lows open leads and polynyas in the sea ice cover, such as the Sirius Water Polynya in northeastern Greenland. Heat loss in polynyas is compensated for by the formation of new ice, and the rejected brine densifies the water on the Greenland shelf. In the Labrador Sea, polar lows intensify cold air outbreaks from the sea ice and rapidly deepen the ocean mixed layer. Resolving polar lows and kinematic features in the sea ice improves the realism of climate models, in particular the surface heat loss and the dense water formation in (sub)polar oceans.

Plain Language Summary We show for the first time that resolving polar lows (strong storms over polar oceans) in a global climate model, which has a high resolution of 2.5 km, leads to strong heat loss from the ocean near the sea ice edge and from leads and polynyas, which are open water areas in an otherwise closed ice cover. Heat loss and salt rejection during ice formation contributes to dense water formation along the sea ice margin and in polynyas above the Greenland shelf. Resolving polar lows and kinematic features in the sea ice improves the realism of climate models, in particular the surface heat loss and the dense water formation in (sub)polar oceans.

1. Introduction

Polar lows (PLs) are the most intense cyclones of the polar mesoscale cyclone family, with subsynoptic scales of less than 1,000 km (Orlanski, 1975) and near-surface wind speeds of more than 15 m s^{-1} that can reach hurricane force ($\geq 33 \text{ m s}^{-1}$). Polar lows form over high-latitude maritime environments poleward of the polar front (Heinemann & Claud, 1997). Although short-lived weather phenomena, they pose a hazard to shipping, air traffic, and offshore installations due to high wind speeds, icing, high waves, poor visibility, and heavy snowfall. The effects of PLs on local weather have been studied since the 1980s using uncoupled regional atmospheric models. However, their effects on climate and the ocean are less well understood (Moreno-Ibáñez et al., 2021), because they are neither resolved nor parameterized in established global climate models. In a first step, we aim to study the effects of PLs on sea ice and the upper ocean in a global coupled kilometer-scale (2.5 km) climate model, analyzing two cases of polar lows, one in the Iceland and Greenland Seas and the other in the Labrador Sea. In this exploratory study, we focus on the effects of PLs on air-sea fluxes near the sea ice margin and from polynyas and leads, as well as on water mass transformation and mixed layer depth.

PLs form over the open ocean and often along the sea ice edge or boundary layer fronts (Rasmussen & Turner, 2003), which are narrow areas of strong temperature gradients or shear and convergence lines. They often develop in association with marine cold air outbreaks (CAOs, Papritz & Spengler, 2017), in which cold and dry polar air is advected over the relatively warm ocean, causing large heat fluxes from the ocean to the atmosphere near the sea ice edge. When a PL forms near the sea ice edge, it can itself trigger a CAO, which amplifies heat loss from the ocean. About 60%–80% of the wintertime heat loss of the subpolar North Atlantic is caused by intermittent CAOs (Smedsrud et al., 2022), about two-thirds of which are accompanied by polar mesoscale cyclogenesis (Terpstra et al., 2021).

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The direct effect of CAOs on the ocean mixed layer and dense water formation have been recently observed in the Iceland Sea (Harden et al., 2015; Renfrew et al., 2023) and in the Greenland Sea (Svingen et al., 2023). The more frequent and more intense the CAOs are during a winter, the deeper the mixed layer becomes. During a CAO in the Iceland Sea, surface heat fluxes of more than 200 W m^{-2} were observed from buoys with wind speeds of 14 m s^{-1} . CAOs typically occur every 1–2 weeks in winter, lasting for 2.5 days on average (Harden et al., 2015). The Iceland and Greenland Seas are both important areas for the formation of dense water (Brakstad et al., 2023; Våge et al., 2022) contributing to the Denmark Strait Overflow Water (DSOW) with a delimiting density of 27.8 kg m^{-3} (Dickson & Brown, 1994). The DSOW leaves the Nordic Seas and becomes part of the deep return branch of the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC, Buckley & Marshall, 2016; Renfrew et al., 2019). From recent observations, it appears that dense water formation east of Greenland is of particular importance to the strength and variability of the AMOC (Lozier et al., 2019), particularly in the Nordic Seas (Chafik & Rossby, 2019).

PLs have been studied almost exclusively with regional atmospheric models (Jung et al., 2016), with recent representations also in global atmosphere models (Bresson et al., 2022). To our knowledge, only two studies have been conducted with coupled models. A 3-day long simulation with a regional model for the Barents Sea with a resolution of 5 km (Wu, 2021) and one with a global model (Hallerstig et al., 2021), with varying resolution in the atmosphere (18–5 km) and a 0.25° ocean. A high horizontal resolution of the atmospheric model leads to a better representation of wind speed (Kolstad, 2015, 2017; Mc Innes et al., 2011), surface heat fluxes, and the atmospheric water cycle (Spensberger & Spengler, 2021) during CAOs, but also of mesoscale wind systems around Greenland (Gutjahr & Heinemann, 2018), such as tip jets (Doyle & Shapiro, 1999; Pickart et al., 2003), katabatic storms, and PLs (Gutjahr et al., 2022; Klein & Heinemann, 2002; Kristjánsson et al., 2011). It has also been recognized that coupling with a dynamical sea ice and ocean model is necessary to improve the simulation of PLs (Jung et al., 2016). A kilometer-scale resolution ($\leq 5 \text{ km}$) in the ocean model improves the representation of small-scale processes, such as ocean eddies or leads and polynyas in the sea ice (Wang et al., 2016). Polynyas are persistent and recurrent areas of open water or thin ice and thus lower ice concentration in an otherwise closed sea ice cover, usually occurring in the same location (Morales Maqueda et al., 2004). Leads, on the other hand, are transient linear openings that can occur everywhere in the ice on very short (subsynoptic) timescales.

Dense water forms not only in the open ocean, but also within coastal polynyas on the Arctic continental shelf, where heat is lost and compensated by the formation of sea ice, releasing brine into the ocean beneath the ice (Cornish et al., 2022). These brine-enriched shelf waters descend down the slopes into deeper layers. If the resolution of the ocean model is too coarse, polynyas are not represented, leading to biases in the properties of the deep water in the Arctic Mediterranean (Heuzé et al., 2023). The fracturing of sea ice has been observed during the passage of synoptic-scale cyclones, increasing the air-sea fluxes, but also enhancing lateral melting (Graham et al., 2019). However, whether PLs affect the sea ice and polynyas due to their much shorter timescale is less clear.

The question, then, is how the ocean and sea ice respond to resolving PLs in a fully coupled climate model of kilometer-scale. Global climate models have reached the kilometer scale (Hohenegger et al., 2023) and are capable of resolving all necessary processes, including mesoscale wind systems and PLs, boundary layer fronts, and deep convection in the atmosphere, mesoscale eddies in the ocean, and leads and polynyas in the sea ice. In the ocean, unresolved (sub)mesoscale processes are thought to be important for the large-scale response of the climate system (Hewitt et al., 2022) and the role of small-scale ocean processes on the large-scale climate needs to be investigated. In this study, we make a first step in this direction by explicitly resolving PLs, ocean eddies, polynyas and leads in a globally coupled simulation of kilometer-scale. We investigate the effects of PLs on the ocean and sea ice using the globally coupled ICON (Icosahedral Nonhydrostatic)-Sapphire model at a horizontal resolution of 2.5 km in the atmosphere, ocean, sea ice and land. Because the simulation is relatively short (72 days), we focus on two case studies of PLs, one over the Iceland and Greenland Seas and one over the Labrador Sea, in which we demonstrate the effect of PLs on the upper ocean and sea ice. The case studies discussed do not have real-time counterparts because the coupled model ran freely after its initialization on 20 January 2020 and therefore followed a different trajectory.

The remainder of the manuscript is organized as follows. In Section 2, the ICON-Sapphire model and its configuration is described. In Section 3 and Section 4, we present the results for the case studies in the Iceland and Greenland Seas and the Labrador Sea, respectively. In Section 5 we summarize the results and draw conclusions.

2. ICON-Sapphire Model Configuration

We use a globally coupled simulation (ICON2.5) produced with ICON-Sapphire (G_AO_2.5km in Hohenegger et al., 2023). ICON-Sapphire is a storm- and eddy-resolving version of ICON-ESM (Jungclaus et al., 2022) under the nextGEMS project (<https://nextgems-h2020.eu/>), which is a successor to DYAMOND Winter (Stevens et al., 2019). The objective of ICON-Sapphire is to use as few parameterizations as possible, retaining only those necessary to represent physical processes that cannot be represented at kilometer scales. ICON2.5 was run at a horizontal resolution of 2.5 km (Figure 1 and Table 1) in both the atmosphere and land (ICON-A, Giorgetta et al., 2018) and ocean/sea ice components (ICON-O, Korn, 2017; Korn et al., 2022) for 3 months (72 days), beginning on 20 January 2020 and ending on 31 March 2020. This high global resolution allows the simulation of PLs in the Nordic Seas such as Iceland, Greenland, and the Norwegian Sea, as well as in the Labrador and Irminger Seas of the subpolar North Atlantic. In the ocean, kinematic features in the sea ice are resolved as well as a large part of the mesoscale eddies in the North and Labrador Seas. We briefly describe the main features of this configuration, a more complete overview can be found in Hohenegger et al. (2023).

2.1. Atmosphere and Land

The atmosphere was initialized from the European Center for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) operational analysis for 20 January 2020. ICON-A used 90 vertical levels, with the top height at 75 km and layer thicknesses ranging from 25 to 400 m, with the lowest full model level at 12.5 m height. In ICON-A, only a minimal set of parameterizations was used, namely for radiation, microphysics, and turbulence. Radiation is parameterized by the Radiative Transfer for Energetics RRTM for General circulation model applications Parallel (RTE-RRTMGP) scheme (Pincus et al., 2019). Microphysics are parameterized with a one-moment scheme (Baldauf et al., 2011), which predicts the specific mass of water vapor, cloud water, rain, cloud ice, snow and graupel. Although all hydrometeors are advected by the dynamics, only cloud water and ice are mixed by the turbulence scheme and are optically active. No parameterization was used for subgrid-scale clouds, so grid boxes are either binary covered by clouds or cloud-free. Turbulence was parameterized with the Smagorinsky scheme (Smagorinsky, 1963) with modifications by Lilly (1962). Surface fluxes were computed according to Louis (1979) with stability functions from Businger et al. (1971) and Dyer (1974). Land processes are simulated by the JSBACH land surface model (Reick et al., 2021).

2.2. Ocean and Sea Ice

The ocean was spun up from a complex simulation (see Hohenegger et al. (2023) for details) forced with climatological, NCEP (Kalnay et al., 1996), and ERA5 (Hersbach et al., 2020) reanalyses using the Polar Science Center Hydrographic Climatology (PHC) version 3.0 observational data set (Steele et al., 2001) as initial conditions. ICON-O used 112 vertical z-levels with a free ocean surface. The thickness of the ocean layers range from 6 to 532 m. Similar to the atmosphere, only a minimal set of parameterizations was used in ICON-O. Velocity dissipation (or friction) was parameterized by a “harmonic” Laplace operator. Turbulent vertical mixing was parameterized based on the turbulent kinetic energy (TKE) equation (Gaspar et al., 1990), in which a mixing length approach for the vertical mixing coefficient for velocity and oceanic tracers is used (Blanke & Delecluse, 1993).

In the current ICON-O version, sea ice thermodynamics are described by a single-category, zero-layer formulation (Semtner, 1976). Sea ice dynamics are based on the dynamics component of the Finite-Element Sea Ice Model (FESIM, Danilov et al., 2015), see Korn et al. (2022). The sea ice model solves the momentum equation for sea ice with an elastic-viscoplastic (EVP) rheology (Hunke & Dukowicz, 1997).

Sea ice growth was not stored as an output variable, so we calculated potential ice production in polynyas from model output (Gutjahr et al., 2016; Zhou et al., 2023). The conductive heat flux through the ice (F_c) is assumed to be balanced by the net surface heat flux Q :

$$F_c = F_{sw} + F_{lw} + F_{sh} + F_{lh} = Q, \quad (1)$$

with F_{sw} and F_{lw} the net shortwave and long wave radiation fluxes, and F_{sh} and F_{lh} the turbulent sensible and latent heat fluxes.

Figure 1. (a) Global sea surface temperature and sea ice concentration simulated by the coupled ICON2.5 (2.5 km horizontal resolution) for 3 February 2020 at 0 UTC. Overlaid is the daily mean 15% sea ice concentration (cyan) from EUMETSAT OSI SAF v3.0 (OSI-450a, Laverne et al., 2019) for the same day with a resolution of 25 km. Overlaid on land is NASA's true color blue marble image from Terra at 0.1° (<https://neo.gsfc.nasa.gov/view.php?datasetId=BlueMarbleNG-TB>). The black boxes in (a) mark the two case study areas, whose bathymetry is shown enlarged in (b) for the Labrador Sea and (c) for the Iceland and Greenland Seas. The black box in (c) shows the area of the Northeast Greenland shelf, which is enlarged in (d). The blue box in (c) and (d) marks the area of the Sirius Water Polynya (SWP).

Ice growth $\frac{\partial h}{\partial t}$ (in m s^{-1}) was computed per grid cell as

$$\frac{\partial h}{\partial t} = \frac{Q - F_o}{\rho_i L_i}, \quad (2)$$

with F_o the ocean heat flux (positive ablates the ice), $\rho_i = 916.7 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ the constant sea ice density, and $L_i = 0.3337 \cdot 10^6 \text{ J kg}^{-1}$ the latent heat of fusion for ice. New ice grows if the ocean is losing heat ($Q - F_o > 0$).

Table 1
Overview of the Globally Coupled ICON-Sapphire 2.5 km Simulation

Parameter	ICON2.5
Horizontal resolution	r2b10 (2.5 km)
# vertical levels (atm/oce)	90/112
Δz -levels (oce)	6–532 m
Δ hybrid σ -levels (atm)	25–400 m (lowest full level at 12.5 m)
Δt (atm/oce)	20 s/80 s
Coupling frequency	12 min
Simulation period	2020-01-20 to 2020-03-31 (72 d)
Output volume	~340 TB (135 TB/month)
Output frequency	2d-atm. (30 min), 3d-atm. (1 d), 2d-oce (1 hr, 3 hr), 3d-oce < 200 m (3 hr), 3d-oce (1 d)

This approach assumes that the seawater is at the freezing temperature and that newly formed ice is immediately transported away, leaving the polynya open.

We then computed the daily ice volume growth within a polynya (sea ice concentration <60%), as follows (Cheng et al., 2017; Zhou et al., 2023):

$$V = tA(1 - SIC) \frac{\partial h}{\partial t}, \quad (3)$$

with $t = 86,400$ s (1 day), SIC the sea ice concentration, and A the area of the grid cell. We used the same threshold of 60% that was used by Pedersen et al. (2010) to compute the area of the SWP. Therefore, only grid cells with SIC <60% were counted for the ice production and computation of the polynya area $A(1 - SIC)$. The total daily ice production (in m^3) was then summed up within the black box shown in Figure 6.

2.3. Data Output Frequency and Preprocessing

The 2d surface fields were available as 30-min averages for the atmosphere and as 1-hr means for the ocean. 3d atmospheric fields were available as daily means and for the ocean the total depth levels were available as daily means and the upper 200 m as 3-hourly means. We have interpolated all ICON2.5 fields onto a regular 2.5 km grid by a nearest-neighbor method.

3. Polar Low in the Iceland and Greenland Seas

The first case study describes the formation of a PL at the sea ice edge in the Iceland Sea. The polar low developed from a preceding mesoscale lee cyclone over the Irminger Sea (not shown). The PL moved along the sea ice edge before crossing the Greenland and Norwegian Seas and reaching the Barents Sea 3 days later (Section 3.1). During its passage, strong northerly winds caused a CAO from the sea ice of the East Greenland Current (EGC), which led to a strong heat loss from the Iceland and Greenland Seas and formed sufficiently dense water to contribute to the DSOW (Section 3.2). Over the northeast Greenland shelf, the strong northerly winds opened leads and polynyas in the sea ice along the coast, such as the Sirius Water Polynya (SWP, Pedersen et al., 2010; Jackson et al., 2022) (Section 3.3) or the Northeast Water (NEW) Polynya (Bennett et al., 2024). Compared to OSI SAF version 3 (Lavergne et al., 2019), the sea ice concentration in ICON2.5 reached too far east in the Iceland and Greenland Seas (see Figure 1), which had an effect on the location of dense water formation, as we will explain below. However, the too southerly sea ice edge does not affect the mechanism of how polar lows interact with the upper ocean and sea ice.

3.1. Polar Low Formation

On 2 February 2020, a mesoscale lee cyclone formed over the Irminger Sea and crossed Iceland. Descending southerly winds from Iceland and their diabatic warming and vorticity stretching led to an increase in positive

(cyclonic) relative vorticity north of Iceland. Furthermore, warm air advection northeast of Iceland contributed to additional cyclonic vorticity generation. Due to these processes, the boundary layer front at the sea ice edge north of Iceland became unstable (visible as a strong shear line with positive vorticity of $\zeta/f > 3.0$ in Figure 2a).

At the same time, an upper-level shortwave trough with a length scale of about $L = 400$ km was present over the Iceland Sea and associated with a positive vorticity (PV) anomaly. Weak stratification below 500 hPa with a mean Brunt-Väisälä frequency of about $N = 8 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at the sea ice edge and a planetary vorticity at 66.9°N of $f = 1.34 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ results in a Rossby penetration depth of about $H = fL/N = 6.7$ km. Therefore, the cyclonic circulation associated with the positive upper-level PV anomaly could easily reach the sea surface and amplify the lower-level positive PV anomaly at the sea ice edge (see Rasmussen and Turner (2003) for a more detailed description of this mechanism).

As a result, the cyclone deepened rapidly, and the core pressure dropped accordingly to about 960 hPa at 0 UTC on 3 February 2020 (Figures 2a and 2b). 18 hours later, the core pressure dropped further to 942 hPa (Figures 2c and 2d) as the upper-level positive PV anomaly and with it the polar low moved northeastward along the sea ice edge. The PL had sharply defined fronts (Figure 2c) and its size was of meso- α scale (Orlanski, 1975), resembling cases in the Greenland Sea described by Rasmussen and Turner (2003). The 10 m wind speed reached hurricane force ($U_{\text{max}} = 34 \text{ m s}^{-1}$) over the sea ice at 18 UTC on 3 February 2020 (Figure 2d) and values of more than 28 m s^{-1} over the Iceland and Greenland Seas. The strong off-ice winds advected cold and dry polar air over the relatively warm Iceland and Greenland Seas in a CAO, which led to large surface heat fluxes.

3.2. Heat Loss From the Ocean and Denmark Strait Overflow Water Formation in Response to a Polar Low

3.2.1. Heat Loss During the Polar Low Passage

Figure 3 shows the evolution of the PL from 3 to 6 February 2020. After its formation at the sea ice edge, the low moved along the ice edge before crossing the open ocean south of Svalbard into the Barents Sea. Strong northerly winds over the sea ice of the EGC caused the ice to break forming leads, which is especially visible on 6 February 2020 (Figure 3e). Polynyas opened up near the northeast coast of Greenland, such as the Scoresby Sund and the Sirius Water polynyas (see Section 3.3), or the Storfjorden Polynya in southern Svalbard.

The strong winds of the PL and the CAO led to strong turbulent heat fluxes near the ice edge in the Iceland Sea, but also over the Greenland Sea as the PL moved northward along the ice edge. During its mature state at 18 UTC on 3 February 2020, the total turbulent (latent + sensible) heat flux (THF) reached values of up to $1,000 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ over the Iceland Sea (Figure 3d). Over the Scoresby Sund and Sirius Water polynyas, the THF was about 400 W m^{-2} . Strong wind speeds further led to a THF of up to $1,000 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ over Fram Strait and the Storfjorden Polynya, which is the primary source for brine-enriched shelf waters in the Nordic Seas (e.g., Skogseth et al., 2004, 2008). When the PL reached the Barents Sea, it caused THF values of more than $1,200 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ due to a CAO from the sea ice over the relatively warm ocean surface of the Barents Sea. Higher surface heat fluxes compared to ERA5 (not shown) could be caused by a warmer sea surface temperature of about $1\text{--}2^\circ\text{C}$ compared to ORAS5 (Zuo et al., 2019) (not shown) and by stronger near-surface wind speeds due to higher resolution. Such a combination of higher surface heat fluxes and more extreme wind speeds during polar lows and CAOs was also found for other simulations (Kolstad, 2015).

Over the Iceland and Greenland Seas, the strong heat fluxes posed a strong buoyancy loss of the upper ocean and hence a potential source for dense water formation. Figure 4a shows the potential density (σ_θ) at the ocean surface during the peak intensity of the polar low at 18 UTC on 3 February 2020. Dense water ($\geq 27.8 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$) emerged to the surface directly along the sea ice edge in the Iceland and Greenland Seas. A density of 27.8 kg m^{-3} is the delimiter for overflow water (Dickson & Brown, 1994). Water denser than or equal to this threshold potentially becomes part of the DSOW, the densest water mass of the Deep Western Boundary Current, and thus part of the lower limb of the AMOC. North of Jan Mayen in the southern Greenland Sea, the outcropping of the 27.8 kg m^{-3} isopycnal was interrupted by buoyant eddies resulting from baroclinic instabilities of the EGC (Foukal et al., 2020) that become part of the reflecting Jan Mayen Current (Bourke et al., 1992). The eddies transported cold and fresh Polar Surface Water into the Greenland Sea, suppressing the formation of dense water. The cold SST of these eddies can be seen from Figure 1a. After the polar low has passed, the surface density at the sea ice edge in the Iceland Sea increased by about $0.05\text{--}0.1 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ (Figure 4c), which preconditioned the water column

Figure 2. ICON2.5 snapshots (30 min means) of (a, c) atmospheric relative vorticity (ζ) at 10 m height scaled by planetary vorticity (f) and (b, d) 10 m wind speed for 2020-02-03 0 UTC and 2020-02-03 18 UTC. Overlaid in all figures is the mean sea-level pressure (pmsl every 4 hPa; solid black contours) and additionally in (c, d) the 2 m temperature in white (dashed for negative, solid for positive). The gray vectors show the wind direction and speed.

for dense water formation (see Section 3.2.2). We note that the surface density in ICON2.5 is lighter compared to ORAS5 (not shown), so that the model underestimates the outcropping densities.

The mixed layer reached depths of more than 400 m in the Iceland Sea south of Jan Mayen and in Fram Strait. Directly at the sea ice edge, the mixed layer in the Iceland Sea deepened by about 200 m within 5 days after the passage of the polar low (Figure 4e), corresponding to a rate of about 40 m d⁻¹, which is consistent with the 38 m d⁻¹ observed with moorings in the Greenland Sea during strong CAOs (Svingen et al., 2023).

3.2.2. Watermass Transformation in the Iceland Sea

To quantify the effect of the PL on the dense water formation, we computed the surface water mass transformation (WMT), $F(\sigma_\theta)$ in units of m³ s⁻¹, for the density class (or bin size) enclosed by the outcropping isopycnal of $\sigma_\theta = 27.85 \pm 0.05$ kg m⁻³, following the approach of Petit et al. (2020) and Speer and Tziperman (1992). We first computed the buoyancy flux (B) at the ocean surface from 6-hourly mean values, following Groeskamp et al. (2019) ($B > 0$ means a buoyancy loss of the sea surface water):

$$B = \overline{w'b'} = -\frac{\alpha}{c_p} Q_0 + \beta \frac{S}{1-S} (E - P), \quad (4)$$

with w' and b' fluctuations of the vertical velocity and buoyancy, $c_p = 4192.664$ J K⁻¹ kg⁻¹ the specific heat capacity of sea water, Q_0 the net heat flux (in W m⁻²) at the ocean surface (positive into the ocean), α (in K⁻¹) and β (in psu⁻¹) the thermal expansion and haline contraction coefficients, S the salinity (in psu), P the precipitation

Figure 3. Evolution of the polar low from 2020-02-03 to 2020-02-06 in ICON2.5: (a, c, e) sea ice concentration (color shaded) and (b, d, f) total turbulent heat flux (latent + sensible, color shaded). The black contours in all figures show the mean sea level pressure (msl, every 4 hPa). Positive values mean a heat flux from the ocean into the atmosphere. The gray vectors show the 10 m wind direction and speed.

(rain + snow + runoff) and E the evaporation (both in $\text{m s}^{-1} \hat{=} \text{kg m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-2}$). ICON-O uses the UNESCO equation of state (UNESCO, 1981) to compute α and β .

Then we calculated $F(\sigma_\theta)$ by integrating the buoyancy flux over the area A of the outcropping density class ($\sigma_\theta + \Delta\sigma_\theta/2$) with $\Delta\sigma_\theta = 0.1$:

$$F(\sigma_\theta) = \frac{1}{\Delta\sigma_\theta} \iint B \Pi(\sigma_\theta) dA, \quad (5)$$

where

$$\Pi(\sigma_\theta) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{for } |\sigma_\theta - \sigma'_\theta| \leq \frac{\Delta\sigma_\theta}{2} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

is a filter that ensures that only the area A enclosed by a density class is integrated. We followed the convention that when $F(\sigma_\theta) > 0$, water is transformed toward a higher density.

Figure 5a shows the WMT to the density class of $\sigma_\theta = 27.85 \pm 0.05 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$, which corresponds to DSOW. During the PL passage (3–6 February 2020), dense water formed near the sea ice edge in the Iceland Sea south of Jan Mayen. As the PL moved north, the area of dense water formation followed the sea ice edge north into the Greenland Sea, with a second peak in the Greenland Gyre area south of Fram Strait. With the PL steering into the Barents Sea, dense water also formed in a narrow band south of Bear Island and extended along the sea ice edge to the east. The relative WMT contribution from the PL (3–6 February 2020) onto the total WMT ranged from about 10 to 30% (Figure 5c), with the highest values near the ice edge in the Iceland Sea and close to Jan Mayen.

As mentioned above, buoyant eddies from the EGC (Figure 4) prevented dense water formation directly at the sea ice edge in our simulation, so that it is displaced farther away from the sea ice in the Iceland and Greenland Seas. However, the sea ice in the Iceland Sea in our ICON2.5 simulation extends too far east compared to present-day conditions (see Figure 1). Therefore, the WMT occurs too far in the central Iceland Sea and not in its northwestern part (Spall et al., 2021; Våge et al., 2018, 2022), as has been observed in connection with a retreating sea ice edge toward Greenland (Moore et al., 2022). Furthermore, we note that our simulation period is rather short and hence longer simulations of a similar resolution are required to quantify the effect of PLs on the climate scale.

A time series of the integrated WMT over the Iceland Sea (Figure 5d; averaged over the black box in Figures 5a–5c) shows peak values of about 17 Sv, with one of the peaks coinciding with the studied PL from 3 to 6 February 2020. The time series shows that there are episodes with high formation rates, which are interspersed with periods of low or no formation. The largest formation rates in the simulation occur about a week after the studied PL (9–15 February), where there was an episode with high WMT for the density class $27.85 \pm 0.05 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$, but even denser water ($27.95 \pm 0.05 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$) formed in the Iceland Sea (Figure A1). This strong WMT event was caused by another polar low that triggered a CAO that peaked in intensity on February 8 and 9, 2020. This PL formed similarly to the one on 3 February, with wind speeds of up to 28 m s over the Iceland Sea, and dissolved on 10 February over Norway when it made landfall. A complex sequence of weaker polar mesoscale cyclones followed in the period from 11 to 15 February embedded in a northwest large-scale flow that continued to advect cold and dry polar air masses over the Iceland Sea in CAOs and led to persistent heat loss from the Iceland Sea. In contrast, the PL on 3 to 6 February advected polar air in a short-lived event over the Iceland Sea after which the wind direction turned to south and interrupted the CAO. The polar low preconditioned the water column in the Iceland Sea so that even denser water ($27.95 \pm 0.05 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$) formed when the next polar low arrived (7–15 February 2020, Figure A1b).

The net formation rate of the $27.85 \pm 0.05 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ class in the simulated winter is about 4.8 Sv (Figures 5d) and 0.6 Sv for the $27.95 \pm 0.05 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ class (Figure A1b). The total WMT calculated from ICON2.5 thus appears to be higher than the average $4.0 \pm 0.7 \text{ Sv}$ for the period 2004–2010 estimated from an inverse box model by Tsubouchi et al. (2021) for the Nordic Seas. Although the rate for the denser class calculated from ICON2.5 agrees with the estimate of $0.7 \pm 0.3 \text{ Sv}$ by Våge et al. (2022) for the periods from fall (September–October) 2015 and late winter (February–April) 2016, where the total WMT fell in the density range of $27.90\text{--}27.95 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$, the main part of the WMT in ICON2.5 is in the lighter density class $27.85 \pm 0.05 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$. However, note that the surface WMT is not directly converted into overflows and that we are looking at a short simulation, which makes it difficult to compare with long-term averages. We cannot conclude whether ICON2.5 systematically produces too high WMT rates or whether this is due to internal variability. For a better comparison, longer kilometer-scale simulations with ICON are needed.

The formation of DSOW strongly depends ($r_s = 0.85, p < 0.01, n = 72$) on whether there is a CAO with a positive temperature gradient of the SST and the 2 m air temperature ($\Delta T = SST - T_{2m}$) and high wind speeds blowing from the sea ice (Figure A2). We find high correlations with both the latent ($r_s = 0.87, p < 0.01, n = 72$) and the

Figure 4. (a) Potential density (σ_θ) at the ocean surface on 2020-02-03 at 18 UTC in ICON2.5. Overlaid as contours in (a) are the mean sea level pressure (light gray, every 4 hPa), the 15% sea ice concentration (a–b: cyan, c, e: gray, d: magenta), the outcropping 27.8 kg m^{-3} (solid white) and 27.9 kg m^{-3} (dashed white) isopycnals, and the mixed layer depth (MLD) exceeding 400 m (orange). (b) daily mean of potential density at the ocean surface in the Iceland Sea on 2020-02-01 before the polar low passage, (c) surface density change on 2020-02-06 after the polar low passage, (d) daily MLD in the Iceland Sea on 2020-02-01 and (e) MLD change on 2020-02-06.

Figure 5. Water mass transformation (WMT), $F(\sigma_\theta)$, of the density class $\sigma_\theta = 27.85 \pm 0.05 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$, which is the threshold density of the DSOW ($1 \text{ mSv} = 10^{-3} \text{ Sv} = 10^3 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$). (a) WMT during the passage of the polar low from 3 to 6 February 2020, (b) total WMT during the simulation period 20 January to 31 March 2020 (72 days), and (c) the relative contribution (%) of the polar low on the total WMT. The blue contour shows the 15% sea ice concentration averaged over 3 to 6 February 2020 in (a) and over 20 January 2020 to 31 March 2020 in (b) and (c). (d) Time series of integrated WMT in the Iceland Sea (black box in a-c). The gray shading marks the period of the polar low passage (3–6 February 2020). The horizontal line marks the net formation rate in winter of about 4.8 Sv from ICON2.5.

sensible heat flux ($r_s = 0.90$, $p < 0.01$, $n = 72$), but only a weak correlation with the wind speed ($r_s = 0.13$, $p = 0.03$, $n = 72$). These results suggest that high wind speed alone is not sufficient for WMT. The wind must come from the ice, advecting cold and dry polar air over the relatively warm sea surface. The heat fluxes caused by the temperature contrast between the sea surface and the atmospheric boundary layer are then considerably intensified by the high wind speed. The correlation coefficients were computed based on Spearman's ρ and the p values were computed based on a two-sided t test.

Our analysis shows that mesoscale PLs contribute to surface WMT and produce dense water along the sea ice edge in the Iceland and Greenland Seas that is above the delimiter (27.8 kg m^{-3}) for DSOW.

3.3. Sirius Water Polynya—Opening and Heat Fluxes During the Polar Low Passage

The Sirius Water Polynya (SWP, Jackson et al., 2022; Pedersen et al., 2010) is one of the most prominent polynyas of Northeast Greenland and located roughly between Clavering Ø and Shannon Ø between 74° and 75°N (Figure 1d). The polynya forms as an intermittent flaw polynya in the transition zone of the fast ice and the pack ice.

Figure 6 shows the sea ice concentration and THF along the northeast coast of Greenland during the passage of the PL. At 0 UTC on 3 February 2020 (Figure 6a), only weak northeasterly winds were blowing in the area of the SWP, after an earlier weaker PL had previously moved along the sea ice off northeastern Greenland, where it also formed sea ice leads and opened the SWP (visible in Figure 6a), resulting in THFs of about $200\text{--}300 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ (Figure 6d). As the PL formed at the sea ice edge in the Denmark Strait, northeasterly winds pushed the ice back

Figure 6. ICON2.5 snapshots over the Sirius Water Polynya showing (a–c) sea ice concentration and (d–f) total turbulent heat flux (THF) at 18 UTC on 3 February 2020, and at 00 UTC and 18 UTC on 6 February 2020, respectively. Positive values mean a heat loss from the ocean. Overlaid is the mean sea level pressure (every 4 hPa, black solid contours) and the 15% sea ice concentration (magenta contour). Wind direction and speed are shown as gray vectors. The black box marks the domain of the Sirius Water Polynya over which quantities were averaged to construct time series (Figure 7).

together east of Scoresby Sund, closing the leads but opening a polynya south of the Blossville coast (Figures 6a–6d).

At 18 UTC on 3 February 2020, the PL reached mature state and moved northeastwards along the sea ice edge. On its backside, the wind turned to the north (Figure 6b) and reached values of up to 34 m s^{-1} in the area of the SWP (Figure 2d). When the wind intensified, the SWP opened (Figure 6b), resulting in a strong heat loss from the ocean of more than 400 W m^{-2} (Figure 6e). The location and size of the SWP is realistically simulated compared to a case study based on satellite data from Pedersen et al. (2010). Although the Scoresby Sund Polynya was still open, there was little heat flux due to the calm wind conditions (Figures 6b and 6c). The northerly winds continued for

the next 3 days until the PL reached the Barents Sea. During this time, the SWP remained open and grew in size until it reached its greatest extent (about $2.13 \cdot 10^3 \text{ km}^2$) on 6 February 2020 (Figure 6c). Since the wind speed was very low on that day, the heat fluxes reached only values of about 200 W m^{-2} . The persistent strong northerly winds had broken up the pack ice, and sea ice leads have formed (Figure 6c), releasing heat with THF values of about $50\text{--}100 \text{ W m}^{-2}$.

3.4. Time Series of the Sirius Water Polynya and Its Control by Polar Lows in Winter 2020

To quantify how polar lows affect the SWP over the entire simulation, we spatially averaged several quantities over the domain marked as a black box in Figure 6. Figure 7 shows these time series of daily means from 20 January to 31 March 2020. There is a clear anticorrelation of low ice concentration and large polynya area (Figure 7a). We have marked all periods in which the SWP opened with Roman numbers (I to VII). The maximum polynya area from ICON2.5 is comparable to the observed value of $1.4 \cdot 10^3 \text{ km}^2$ from Pedersen et al. (2010) for February to May 2008, but often exceeds it, with the largest opening simulated for early February 2020 with $2.13 \cdot 10^3 \text{ km}^2$. The somewhat larger polynya area can have several reasons, such as different environmental conditions that prevailed in the winters of 2008 and 2020, or tuning of the sea ice rheology in our simulation.

At the beginning of each of these periods, the averaged daily wind speed shows a peak of about 20 m s^{-1} with a northerly to northeasterly direction (Figure 7b) and a subsequent weakening. The polynya area and 10 m wind speed show the strongest correlation when the wind speed leads by 1 day (lag1-correlation: $r_s = 0.64$, $p < 0.01$, $n = 72$). The correlation coefficient was computed based on Spearman's ρ and the p value was computed based on a two-sided t test. This delayed response arises from the inertia of sea ice, but it is fast enough for the ice to respond to short-lived PLs. The wind peaks can be seen even more clearly in the 30-min data (orange line in Figure 7b).

Each polynya opening is associated with a THF peak that leads to new ice formation (Figure 7c), while ice formation outside of opening events is significantly reduced. During the opening event from February 3 to 7 (Event II), which was triggered by the investigated PL in the Iceland and Greenland Seas, the new ice production reached a peak value of $0.4 \text{ km}^3 \text{ d}^{-1}$, which corresponds to an average production of 20 cm d^{-1} over the polynya area of about $2 \cdot 10^3 \text{ km}^2$. This number has to be interpreted as the potential ice growth, because we assume that the ocean remains ice free during the polynya opening.

Each of these polynya opening events is associated with northerly winds of a polar low east of northeast Greenland (Figure 8). All these PLs produce wind speeds above gale force in the area of the SWP. These results confirm that PLs drive the opening of the SWP and subsequent heat loss from the ocean, leading to new ice growth and associated brine rejection that densifies the water over the Greenland continental shelf, especially the Polar Surface and Intermediate Water (not shown). In the simulation, the maximum surface density during the SWP openings reached values of about 27.4 kg m^{-3} . The water formed in the SWP therefore does not contribute to the DSOW, but to the salt-enriched shelf water off the coast of northeast Greenland.

4. Polar Low in the Labrador Sea

In the second case study, we analyzed a PL that formed over the Labrador Sea during a CAO from Baffin Island that considerably intensified when it encountered a boundary layer front at the sea ice edge (Section 4.1). The PL is the strongest event in the simulation and caused a considerable heat loss from the open ocean, which directly cooled the Labrador Current and deepened the mixed layer. Additional heat was lost from polynyas along the coast of Labrador (Section 4.2).

4.1. Formation of a Hurricane-Like Polar Low

Initially, a weaker precursor PL had formed at the sea ice edge during a CAO and a short-wave trough at height, which reached its mature stage at 0 UTC on 20 February 2020 (this PL can be seen in Figure 11a). This precursor PL intensified the CAO south of its core, so that strong winds were blowing parallel to the sea ice edge along the Labrador coast. These winds parallel to the sea ice edge occurred below a short-wave trough aloft and destabilized the boundary layer front from which a baroclinic cyclone formed. This destabilizing mechanism by winds parallel to the sea ice edge is known to trigger polar lows (Drüe & Heinemann, 2001; Heinemann, 1996). The baroclinic cyclone was then steered north toward the sea ice and quickly intensified by reaching the sea ice edge at 12 UTC on 21 February 2020. The core pressure dropped to 944 hPa and the winds intensified to hurricane force

(34 m s^{-1} ; Figures 9a and 9b). Over the next 24 hr, the PL steered to the south over the Labrador Sea before crossing into the Irminger Sea south of Cape Farewell, where it merged with a lee vortex.

The baroclinic intensification was driven by the large temperature gradients across the boundary layer front along the sea ice that resulted in strong differential diabatic heating. This strong temperature contrast can be seen from the surface and 2 m temperature fields (Figures 9c and 9d). The warm core of the PL is clearly visible from the 2 m temperature field. In addition, warm signatures from sea ice leads can be seen in the Baffin Bay and from coastal polynyas along the Labrador coast and around smaller island of Baffin Island, such as Resolution Island in front of the Meta Incognita Peninsula. This result shows how resolving leads and polynyas imprints warm anomalies on the atmospheric boundary layer over sea ice, also by warm plumes that can extend several hundred kilometers downstream of polynyas (e.g., Ebner et al., 2011; Gutjahr et al., 2016). The warmer near-surface temperatures could contribute to mediate the too cold atmospheric boundary layer over wintertime sea ice seen in CMIP6 models (Davy & Outten, 2020), although this cold bias appears to result from too warm reanalyses, such as ERA5, due to incorrect snow cover (Batra & Müller, 2019) and is reduced when compared to satellite data (Tian et al., 2024).

4.2. Heat Fluxes and Mixed Layer Deepening

Figure 10a shows the sea ice concentration at 12 UTC on 21 February 2020, where sea ice leads and polynyas can be clearly identified. The PL triggered a strong CAO to the south of its core. The wind speeds of hurricane force induced THF values greater than $3,000 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ over the open water at the sea ice margin (Figure 10b) that directly cooled the boundary current (Labrador Current). Large THFs of about $2,000 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ were also simulated further south over the Labrador Sea near the sea ice. The sea ice broke south of the PL, forming leads and polynyas from which the ocean lost about $200\text{--}1,000 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ of heat. Further north, THF values of 200 W m^{-2} were simulated over sea ice leads and less compact pack ice in the Baffin Bay in relation to strong northerly winds.

Splitting the THF into the sensible and latent heat flux (Figures 10c and 10d) clearly shows that the sensible heat flux is larger close to the sea ice edge and in leads and polynyas (Bowen ratio >1). However, the ocean surface temperature of the Labrador Sea is warmer (about $+1\text{--}2^\circ\text{C}$) than in the reanalysis data of ORAS5 (not shown), which could lead to an overestimation of the heat fluxes in ICON2.5. Although not the focus of this study, the strong heat fluxes near the PL core may cause the warm core as explained by the WISHE (wind-induced surface heat exchange) mechanism. This mechanism intensifies the PL in a positive feedback, as was shown by Wu (2021) for the Barents Sea.

The strong heat fluxes caused a buoyancy loss of the upper-ocean that rapidly deepened the mixed layer. Figure 11a shows the mixed layer depth (MLD) during the precursor PL at 0 UTC on 20 February 2020. Values of up to 800 m were simulated along the concave sea ice edge that decrease away from the sea ice. Buoyant mesoscale eddies shedding from the relatively warm Irminger Current (among them so called Irminger Rings) west of Greenland inhibited deep mixed layers in the northern part of the Labrador Sea.

About 1 day later (Figure 11b), during the mature phase of the studied PL at 18 UTC on 21 February 2020 (Figures 11d and 11f), the average MLD of 490 m over the open ocean in the southwest Labrador Sea has deepened by about 50 m (Figure 11h). Higher values were reached directly at the sea ice edge. Another day later, after the PL has moved into the Irminger Sea (Figures 11c, 11e, and 11g), the MLD has deepened by about 90 m, with again higher values near the ice edge. The deepening rates of the MLD compare well with direct measurements with Langrangian floats (Steffen & D'Asaro, 2002) (see their Figure 5a).

5. Summary and Conclusions

We demonstrate for the first time the explicit simulation of polar lows and their effects on the upper-ocean and sea ice in a globally coupled climate model (ICON) with kilometer-scale resolution (2.5 km). The simulation is able to resolve all relevant processes that are important for the formation of polar lows, such as sharp boundary layer fronts in the atmosphere, and for their effect on the ocean, including mesoscale eddies and polynyas and leads in the sea ice. In a 72-day long simulation, we studied two polar low cases to analyze their effects on the ocean and sea ice: one in the Iceland and Greenland Seas, and one in the Labrador Sea.

In conclusion, our results support that polar lows forming at the sea ice edge induce cold air outbreaks that in combination with the high wind speeds cause considerable heat fluxes from the ocean. Although ICON2.5

Figure 7. Time series of daily means for the entire ICON2.5 simulation period (20 January to 31 March 2020) of (a) sea ice concentration and polynya area (sum of area with $<60\%$ ice concentration), (b) 10 m wind speed (30-min values of the case study in orange) and direction, and (c) net heat flux and new ice formation. The Roman numbers (I–VII) and gray shading mark seven opening events of the Sirius Water Polynya in the ICON2.5 simulation.

simulates warmer SSTs (about $+1$ to $+2^\circ\text{C}$) in the Nordic Seas and the Labrador Sea compared to a coarser ocean reanalysis (ORAS5) and stronger near-surface winds due to a higher resolution than ERA5, the interactions between polar lows and the upper ocean and sea ice are realistically captured. However, the combination of strong winds and warmer SSTs leads to larger heat fluxes than simulated in ERA5 and thus to larger derived WMTs in the Iceland Sea from this ICON simulation.

The high surface heat fluxes lead to dense water formation, which may contribute to the DSO in the Iceland and Greenland Seas, as observed in the Iceland Sea (Renfrew et al., 2023; Våge et al., 2015). Polar lows cause a rapid deepening of the mixed layer with rates of about 50 m d^{-1} , which is in accordance to observations in the Greenland Sea (Svingen et al., 2023) and in the Labrador Sea (Steffen & D’Asaro, 2002). At the coast, the high wind speeds of up to hurricane force (34 m s^{-1}) cause a divergent wind field that opens polynyas, such as the Sirius Water Polynya over the northeast Greenland shelf. Heat loss of about 400 W m^{-2} is balanced by new ice formation, which releases brine and densifies the water on the northeast Greenland shelf. The resulting brine-enriched shelf water in ICON2.5 is, however, too light to contribute to the DSO.

Figure 8. ICON2.5 snapshots of the 10 m wind field (color shaded) and mean sea level pressure (contours; every 4 hPa) during opening events of the Sirius Water Polynya. The magenta contours show the 15% sea ice concentration (SIC). The orange areas depict the maximum polynya area ($0 \leq \text{SIC} \leq 60\%$) within 3 days after the polar low shown. Only coastal polynyas within the black box are displayed. The Roman numbers mark the event in the time series from Figure 7a. Event number III has been left out because the polynya opening is rather weak compared to the other events.

The calculated WMT based on this ICON2.5 simulation is larger than estimates from observations or inverse box models. Based on the data available from this short ICON2.5 simulation, we cannot conclude whether the surface heat fluxes are systematically overestimated by the model. If so, the induced WMT and the mixed layer response will also be overestimated. Clearly, more coupled simulations with kilometer-scale resolutions but longer integration times are needed to verify the polar low induced WMT rates found in this ICON2.5 simulation.

Figure 9. ICON2.5 snapshots of the Labrador Sea and Baffin Bay at 12 UTC on 21 February 2020 showing (a) scaled relative vorticity (ζ/f), (b) 10 m wind speed (U10; color shaded) and vectors (gray arrows), (c) surface temperature (Ts), and (d) 2 m temperature (T2m). Overlaid is the mean sea level pressure (pmsl) as gray contours (every 4 hPa) and the 15% sea ice concentration (magenta).

Figure 10. ICON2.5 snapshots of the Labrador Sea and Baffin Bay at 12 UTC on 21 February 2020 showing (a) sea ice concentration (SIC), (b) total turbulent heat flux (THF), (c) sensible heat flux (SHF), and (d) latent heat flux (LHF). Overlaid is the mean sea level pressure (pmsl) as gray contours (every 4 hPa) and the 15% sea ice concentration (magenta). Note the nonlinear colorbar in (b)–(d).

Figure 11. ICON2.5 snapshots of the Labrador Sea and Baffin Bay at 12 UTC on 21 February 2020 showing the mixed layer depth (MLD) on 20 February at (a) 0 UTC, (b) 18 UTC, and (c) on 22 February at 12 UTC. The difference of (b) minus (a) is shown in (d) and (c) minus (a) in (e), with enlargements of the Labrador Sea in (f–g) marked as a black box in (d) and (e). Overlaid is the mean sea level pressure (pmsl) as gray contours (every 4 hPa) and the 15% sea ice concentration (magenta). (h) density plot of the MLDs in the southwest Labrador within the box shown in (f, g) before (2020-02-20T00:00), during (2020-02-21T12:00), and after (2020-02-22T12:00) the passage of the polar low. The vertical lines mark the mean MLD at the specific dates.

These results demonstrate the importance of resolving mesoscale polar lows in global climate models in order to simulate the strong heat loss of polar oceans and the formation of polynyas and leads in the sea ice. Our findings confirm the results of Condron and Renfrew (2013) but now based on a fully coupled global model. How such mesoscale wind systems contribute to the overflow water on climatic time scales remains an active area of research. Capturing PLs and their effects on the ocean and sea ice requires kilometer-scale resolution in all components, namely the atmosphere, ocean, and sea ice. Resolving polar lows and kinematic features in the sea ice improves the realism of climate models, which is a step forward to improve the representation of surface heat loss, dense water formation, and new ice formation in (sub)polar oceans.

Appendix A: Water Mass Transformation in the Iceland Sea

Figure A1.

In the Iceland Sea, dense water ($\geq 27.8 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$) contributing to the Denmark Strait Overflow Water (DSOW) forms near the sea ice edge. An analysis of WMT for two density classes ($27.85 \pm 0.05 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ and $27.95 \pm 0.05 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$) shows that during the studied PL, dense water of the first class formed, but not of the second class. Whereas around 15. February 2020, also water of density 27.90 kg m^{-3} – $28.0 \pm 0.05 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ formed. This denser water resulted from a persistent heat loss that was caused by a complex interaction of polar mesoscale cyclones that sustained advection of cold polar air from over the sea ice over the Iceland Sea.

The WMT in the Iceland Sea was caused by strong off-ice wind speeds blowing over an air-sea temperature gradient of the sea surface temperature (SST) and the temperature in the atmospheric boundary layer (Figure A2). The cold air outbreak induced by polar lows amplified the heat loss and hence the WMT.

Figure A1. ICON2.5 6-hourly time series averaged over the Iceland Sea (black box in Figure 5) from 20 January to 31 March 2020 showing water mass transformation (WMT) of the density class (a) $27.85 \pm 0.05 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ and (b) $27.95 \pm 0.05 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$. The gray horizontal line marks the net formation rate over the winter (20 January to 31 March 2020), with 4.8 Sv ($\sigma_\theta = 27.85 \pm 0.05 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$) and 0.6 Sv ($\sigma_\theta = 27.95 \pm 0.05 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$). The black vertical line marks the 3 February when the cold air outbreak from the studied PL was strongest over the Iceland Sea.

Figure A2. ICON2.5 6-hourly time series averaged over the Iceland Sea (black box in Figure 5) from 20 January to 31 March 2020 showing water mass transformation (WMT) to the $27.85 \pm 0.05 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ density class and (a) 10 m wind speed, (b) wind direction at 10 m height, and (c) the gradient of the sea surface temperature (SST) and the 2 m temperature (T_{2m}).

Data Availability Statement

The ICON2.5 simulation was performed by Hohenegger et al. (2023) and the source code can be retrieved from Hohenegger (2022). The ICON model is available at <https://www.icon-model.org> under a permissive open source licence (BSD-3C). By downloading the ICON source code, the user accepts the licence agreement. For OSI SAF version 3 (OSI-450a) we acknowledge the EUMETSAT Ocean and Sea Ice Satellite Application Facility. Global sea ice concentration [interim] climate data record 1978–2020 [2021–2022]. Norwegian and Danish Meteorological Institutes. Available from osisaf.met.no., https://doi.org/10.15770/EUM_SAF_OSI_0013 [EUM_SAF_OSI_0014] [last accessed 15 March 2023]. Primary data to reproduce the figures and analysis of the paper can be retrieved for data from Gutjahr and Mehlmann (2023b) and for scripts from Gutjahr and Mehlmann (2023a).

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References

- Baldauf, M., Seifert, A., Förstner, J., Majewski, D., Raschendorfer, M., & Reinhardt, T. (2011). Operational convective-scale numerical weather prediction with the COSMO model: Description and sensitivities. *Monthly Weather Review*, *139*(12), 3887–3905. <https://doi.org/10.1175/MWR-D-10-05013.1>
- Batrak, Y., & Müller, M. (2019). On the warm bias in atmospheric reanalyses induced by the missing snow over Arctic sea-ice. *Nature Communications*, *10*(1), 4170. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-11975-3>
- Bennett, M. G., Renfrew, I. A., Stevens, S., & Moore, G. W. K. (2024). The Northeast Water Polynya, Greenland: Climatology, atmospheric forcing and ocean response. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, *129*(5), e2023JC020513. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2023JC020513>
- Blanke, B., & Delecluse, P. (1993). Variability of the tropical Atlantic Ocean simulated by a general circulation model with two different mixed-layer physics. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, *23*(7), 1363–1388. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0485\(1993\)023<1363:VOTTAO>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0485(1993)023<1363:VOTTAO>2.0.CO;2)
- Bourke, R. H., Paquette, R. G., & Blythe, R. F. (1992). The Jan Mayen Current of the Greenland Sea. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, *97*(C5), 7241–7250. <https://doi.org/10.1029/92JC00150>
- Brakstad, A., Gebbie, G., Våge, K., Jeansson, E., & Ólafsdóttir, S. R. (2023). Formation and pathways of dense water in the Nordic Seas based on a regional inversion. *Progress in Oceanography*, *212*, 102981. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.poccean.2023.102981>
- Bresson, H., Hodges, K. I., Shaffrey, L. C., Zappa, G., & Schiemann, R. (2022). The response of northern hemisphere polar lows to climate change in a 25 km high-resolution global climate model. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, *127*(4), e2021JD035610. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021JD035610>
- Buckley, M. W., & Marshall, J. (2016). Observations, inferences, and mechanisms of the Atlantic Meridional overturning circulation: A review. *Reviews of Geophysics*, *54*(1), 5–63. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2015RG000493>
- Businger, J. A., Wyngaard, J. C., Izumi, Y., & Bradley, E. F. (1971). Flux-profile relationships in the atmospheric surface layer. *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, *28*(2), 181–189. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0469\(1971\)028<0181:FPRITA>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0469(1971)028<0181:FPRITA>2.0.CO;2)
- Chafik, L., & Rossby, T. (2019). Volume, heat, and freshwater divergences in the subpolar North Atlantic suggest the Nordic Seas as key to the state of the meridional overturning circulation. *Geophysical Research Letters*, *46*(9), 4799–4808. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019GL082110>
- Cheng, Z., Pang, X., Zhao, X., & Tan, C. (2017). Spatio-temporal variability and model parameter sensitivity analysis of ice production in Ross ice shelf polynya from 2003 to 2015. *Remote Sensing*, *9*(9), 934. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs9090934>
- Condron, A., & Renfrew, I. A. (2013). The impact of polar mesoscale storms on northeast Atlantic Ocean circulation. *Nature Geoscience*, *6*(1), 34–37. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ngeo1661>
- Cornish, S. B., Johnson, H. L., Mallett, R. D. C., Dörr, J., Kostov, Y., & Richards, A. E. (2022). Rise and fall of sea ice production in the Arctic Ocean's ice factories. *Nature Communications*, *13*(1), 7800. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-34785-6>
- Danilov, S., Wang, Q., Timmermann, R., Iakovlev, N., Sidorenko, D., Kimritz, M., et al. (2015). Finite-element sea ice model (FESIM), version 2. *Geoscientific Model Development*, *8*(6), 1747–1761. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-8-1747-2015>
- Davy, R., & Outten, S. (2020). The Arctic surface climate in CMIP6: Status and developments since CMIP5. *Journal of Climate*, *33*(18), 8047–8068. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-19-0990.1>
- Dickson, R., & Brown, J. (1994). The production of North Atlantic deep water: Source rates and pathways. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, *99*(C6), 12319–12341. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI3885.1>
- Doyle, J. D., & Shapiro, M. A. (1999). Flow response to large-scale topography: The Greenland tip jet. *Tellus*, *51*(5), 728–748. <https://doi.org/10.3402/tellusa.v51i5.14471>
- Drüe, C., & Heinemann, G. (2001). Airborne investigation of Arctic boundary-layer fronts over the marginal ice zone of the Davis Strait. *Boundary-Layer Meteorology*, *101*(2), 261–292. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1019223513815>
- Dyer, A. J. (1974). A review of flux-profile relationships. *Boundary-Layer Meteorology*, *7*(3), 363–372. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00240838>
- Ebner, L., Schröder, D., & Heinemann, G. (2011). Impact of Laptev Sea flaw polynyas on the atmospheric boundary layer and ice production using idealized mesoscale simulations. *Polar Research*, *30*(1), 7210. <https://doi.org/10.3402/polar.v30i0.7210>
- Foukal, N. P., Gelderloos, R., & Pickart, R. S. (2020). A continuous pathway for fresh water along the East Greenland shelf. *Science Advances*, *6*(43), eabc4254. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.abc4254>
- Gaspar, P., Grégoris, Y., & Lefevre, J.-M. (1990). A simple eddy kinetic energy model for simulations of the oceanic vertical mixing: Tests at station Papa and long-term upper ocean study site. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, *95*(C9), 16179–16193. <https://doi.org/10.1029/JC095iC09p16179>
- Giorgetta, M. A., Brokopf, R., Cruieger, T., Esch, M., Fiedler, S., Helmert, J., et al. (2018). ICON-A, the atmosphere component of the ICON Earth system model: I. Model description. *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems*, *10*(7), 1613–1637. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2017MS001242>
- Graham, R. M., Itkin, P., Meyer, A., Sundfjord, A., Spreen, G., Smedsrud, L. H., et al. (2019). Winter storms accelerate the demise of sea ice in the Atlantic sector of the Arctic Ocean. *Scientific Reports*, *9*(1), 2045–2322. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-45574-5>
- Groeskamp, S., Griffies, S. M., Iudicone, D., Marsh, R., Nurser, A. J. G., & Zika, J. D. (2019). The water mass transformation framework for ocean physics and biogeochemistry. *Annual Review of Marine Science*, *11*(1), 271–305. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-marine-010318-095421>
- Gutjahr, O., & Heinemann, G. (2018). A model-based comparison of extreme winds in the Arctic and around Greenland. *International Journal of Climatology*, *38*(14), 5272–5292. <https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.5729>
- Gutjahr, O., Heinemann, G., Preußner, A., Willmes, S., & Drüe, C. (2016). Quantification of ice production in Laptev Sea polynyas and its sensitivity to thin-ice parameterizations in a regional climate model. *The Cryosphere*, *10*(6), 2999–3019. <https://doi.org/10.5194/tc-10-2999-2016>
- Gutjahr, O., Jungclaus, J. H., Brüggemann, N., Haak, H., & Marotzke, J. (2022). Air-sea interactions and water mass transformation during a katabatic storm in the Irminger Sea. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, *127*(5), e2021JC018075. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021JC018075>
- Gutjahr, O., & Mehlmann, C. (2023a). *Polar lows and their effects on sea ice and the upper ocean in the Iceland, Greenland and Labrador Seas—Icon-Sapphire 2.5 km data*. World Data Center for Climate (WDCC) at DKRZ. Retrieved from <https://hdl.handle.net/21.14106/c66d15d1a10c322cd4d94e60a11ea8e9386c9707>
- Gutjahr, O., & Mehlmann, C. (2023b). *Polar lows and their effects on sea ice and the upper ocean in the Iceland, Greenland and Labrador Seas—Scripts*. MPG.PuRe. Retrieved from <https://hdl.handle.net/21.11116/0000-000D-4D7D-2>
- Hallerstig, M., Magnusson, L., Kolstad, E. W., & Mayer, S. (2021). How grid-spacing and convection representation affected the wind speed forecasts of four polar lows. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, *147*(734), 150–165. <https://doi.org/10.1002/qj.3911>
- Harden, B. E., Renfrew, I. A., & Petersen, G. N. (2015). Meteorological buoy observations from the central Iceland Sea. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, *120*(8), 3199–3208. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2014JD022584>

- Heinemann, G. (1996). On the development of wintertime meso-scale cyclones near the sea ice front in the Arctic and Antarctic. *The Global Atmosphere and Ocean System*, 4, 89–121.
- Heinemann, G., & Claud, C. (1997). “Report of a workshop on theoretical and observational studies of polar lows” of the European geophysical society polar lows working group. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 78(11), 2643–2658. <https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0477-78.11.2643>
- Hersbach, H., Bell, B., Berrisford, P., Hirahara, S., Horányi, A., Muñoz-Sabater, J., et al. (2020). The ERA5 global reanalysis. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, 146(730), 1999–2049. <https://doi.org/10.1002/qj.3803>
- Heuzé, C., Zanowski, H., Karam, S., & Muilwijk, M. (2023). The deep Arctic Ocean and Fram strait in CMIP6 models. *Journal of Climate*, 36(8), 2551–2584. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-22-0194.1>
- Hewitt, H., Fox-Kemper, B., Pearson, B., Roberts, M., & D. K. (2022). The small scales of the ocean may hold the key to surprises. *Nature Climate Change*, 12(6), 496–499. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-022-01386-6>
- Hohenegger, C. (2022). Code for “ICON-Sapphire: Simulating the components of the Earth system and their interactions at kilometer and subkilometer scales”. *Edmond*. <https://doi.org/10.17617/3.1XTSR6>
- Hohenegger, C., Korn, P., Linardakis, L., Redler, R., Schnur, R., Adamidis, P., et al. (2023). ICON-sapphire: Simulating the components of the Earth system and their interactions at kilometer and subkilometer scales. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 16(2), 779–811. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-16-779-2023>
- Hoyer, S., & Hamman, J. (2017). xarray: N-D labeled arrays and datasets in Python. *Journal of Open Research Software*, 5(1), 10. <https://doi.org/10.5334/jors.148>
- Hunke, E. C., & Dukowicz, J. K. (1997). An elastic–viscous–plastic model for sea ice dynamics. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, 27(9), 1849–1867. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0485\(1997\)027<1849:AEVPMF>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0485(1997)027<1849:AEVPMF>2.0.CO;2)
- Jackson, R., Andreasen, N., Oksman, M., Andersen, T. J., Pearce, C., Seidenkrantz, M.-S., & Ribeiro, S. (2022). Marine conditions and development of the Sirius water polynya on the North-East Greenland shelf during the younger dryas-holocene. *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 291, 107647. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2022.107647>
- Jung, T., Gordon, N. D., Bauer, P., Bromwich, D. H., Chevallier, M., Day, J. J., et al. (2016). Advancing polar prediction capabilities on daily to seasonal time scales. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 97(9), 1631–1647. <https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-14-00246.1>
- Jungclaus, J., Lorenz, S., Schmidt, H., Brovkin, V., Brüggemann, N., Chegini, F., et al. (2022). The ICON Earth system model version 1.0. *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems*, 14(4), e2021MS002813. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021MS002813>
- Kalnay, E., Kanamitsu, M., Kistler, R., Collins, W., Deaven, D., Gandin, L., et al. (1996). The NCEP/NCAR 40-year reanalysis project. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 77(3), 437–472. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0477\(1996\)077<0437:TNYRP>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0477(1996)077<0437:TNYRP>2.0.CO;2)
- Klein, T., & Heinemann, G. (2002). Interaction of katabatic winds and mesocyclones near the eastern coast of Greenland. *Meteorological Applications*, 9(4), 407–422. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1350482702004036>
- Kolstad, E. W. (2015). Extreme small-scale wind episodes over the Barents Sea: When, where and why? *Climate Dynamics*, 45(7–8), 2137–2150. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-014-2462-4>
- Kolstad, E. W. (2017). Higher ocean wind speeds during marine cold air outbreaks. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, 143(706), 2084–2092. <https://doi.org/10.1002/qj.3068>
- Korn, P. (2017). Formulation of an unstructured grid model for global ocean dynamics. *Journal of Comparative Physiology*, 339, 525–552. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcp.2017.03.009>
- Korn, P., Brüggemann, N., Jungclaus, J. H., Lorenz, S. J., Gutjahr, O., Haak, H., et al. (2022). ICON-O: The Ocean component of the ICON Earth system model—Global simulation characteristics and local telescoping capability. *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems*, 14(10), e2021MS002952. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021MS002952>
- Kristjánsson, J. E., Thorsteinsson, S., Kolstad, E. W., & Blechschmidt, A.-M. (2011). Orographic influence of east Greenland on a polar low over the Denmark Strait. *Quarterly Journal of the Meteorological Society*, 137(660), 1773–1789. <https://doi.org/10.1002/qj.831>
- Lavergne, T., Sørensen, A. M., Kern, S., Tonboe, R., Notz, D., Aaboe, S., et al. (2019). Version 2 of the EUMETSAT OSI SAF and ESA CCI sea-ice concentration climate data records. *The Cryosphere*, 13(1), 49–78. <https://doi.org/10.5194/tc-13-49-2019>
- Lilly, D. K. (1962). On the numerical simulation of buoyant convection. *Tellus*, 14(2), 148–172. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2153-3490.1962.tb00128.x>
- Louis, J.-F. (1979). A parametric model of vertical eddy fluxes in the atmosphere. *Boundary-Layer Meteorology*, 17(2), 187–202. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00117978>
- Lozier, M. S., Li, F., Bacon, S., Bahr, F., Bower, A. S., Cunningham, S. A., et al. (2019). A sea change in our view of overturning in the subpolar North Atlantic. *Science*, 363(6426), 516–521. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aau6592>
- May, R. M., Goebbert, K. H., Thielen, J. E., Leeman, J. R., Camron, M. D., Bruick, Z., et al. (2022). MetPy: A meteorological Python library for data analysis and visualization. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 103(10), E2273–E2284. <https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-21-0125.1>
- Mc Innes, H., Kristiansen, J., Kristjánsson, J. E., & Schyberg, H. (2011). The role of horizontal resolution for polar low simulations. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, 137(660), 1674–1687. <https://doi.org/10.1002/qj.849>
- Moore, G. W. K., Våge, K., Renfrew, I. A., & Pickart, R. S. (2022). Sea-ice retreat suggests re-organization of water mass transformation in the Nordic and Barents Seas. *Nature Communications*, 13(67), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-27641-6>
- Morales Maqueda, M. A., Willmott, A. J., & Biggs, N. R. T. (2004). Polynya dynamics: A review of observations and modeling. *Reviews of Geophysics*, 42(1). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2002RG000116>
- Moreno-Ibáñez, M., Laprise, R., & Gachon, P. (2021). Recent advances in polar low research: Current knowledge, challenges and future perspectives. *Tellus A: Dynamic Meteorology and Oceanography*, 73(1), 1–31. <https://doi.org/10.1080/16000870.2021.1890412>
- Orlanski, I. (1975). A rational subdivision of scales for atmospheric processes. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 56(5), 527–530.
- Papritz, L., & Spengler, T. (2017). A Lagrangian Climatology of wintertime cold air outbreaks in the Irminger and Nordic Seas and their role in shaping air–sea heat fluxes. *Journal of Climate*, 30(8), 2717–2737. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-16-0605.1>
- Pedersen, J. B. T., Kaufmann, L. H., Kroon, A., & Jakobsen, B. H. (2010). The Northeast Greenland Sirius Water Polynya dynamics and variability inferred from satellite imagery. *Geografisk Tidsskrift-Danish Journal of Geography*, 110(2), 131–142. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00167223.2010.10669503>
- Petit, T., Lozier, M. S., Josey, S. A., & Cunningham, S. A. (2020). Atlantic deep water formation occurs primarily in the Iceland basin and Irminger Sea by local buoyancy forcing. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 47(22), e2020GL091028. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020GL091028>
- Pickart, R. S., Spall, M. A., Ribergaard, M. H., Moore, G. W. K., & Milliff, R. F. (2003). Deep convection in the Irminger Sea forced by the Greenland tip jet. *Nature*, 424(6945), 152–156. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature01729>

- Pincus, R., Mlawer, E. J., & Delamere, J. S. (2019). Balancing accuracy, efficiency, and flexibility in radiation calculations for dynamical models. *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems*, *11*(10), 3074–3089. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019MS001621>
- Rasmussen, E. A., & Turner, J. (2003). *Polar lows: Mesoscale weather systems in the polar regions*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511524974>
- Reick, H., Gayler, V., Goll, D., Hagemann, S., Heidkamp, M., Nabel, J. E. M. S., et al. (2021). JSBACH 3—The land component of the MPI Earth system model: Documentation of version 3.2. *Berichte zur Erdsystemforschung*, *240*. <https://doi.org/10.17617/2.3279802>
- Renfrew, I. A., Huang, J., Semper, S., Barrell, C., Terpstra, A., Pickart, R. S., et al. (2023). Coupled atmosphere–ocean observations of a cold-air outbreak and its impact on the Iceland Sea. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, *149*(751), 472–493. <https://doi.org/10.1002/qj.4418>
- Renfrew, I. A., Pickart, R. S., Våge, K., Moore, G. W. K., Bracegirdle, T. J., Elvidge, A. D., et al. (2019). The Iceland Greenland seas project. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, *100*(9), 1795–1817. <https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-18-0217.1>
- Semtner, A. J. (1976). A model for the thermodynamic growth of sea ice in numerical investigations of climate. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, *6*(3), 379–389. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0485\(1976\)006<0379:AMFTTG>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0485(1976)006<0379:AMFTTG>2.0.CO;2)
- Skogseth, R., Haugan, P. M., & Haarpaintner, J. (2004). Ice and brine production in Storfjorden from four winters of satellite and in situ observations and modeling. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, *109*(C10). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2004JC002384>
- Skogseth, R., Smedsrud, L. H., Nilsen, F., & Fer, I. (2008). Observations of hydrography and downflow of brine-enriched shelf water in the Storfjorden polynya, Svalbard. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, *113*(C8). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2007JC004452>
- Smagorinsky, J. (1963). General circulation experiments with the primitive equations. *Monthly Weather Review*, *91*(3), 99–164. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493\(1963\)091<0099:GCEWTP>2.3.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493(1963)091<0099:GCEWTP>2.3.CO;2)
- Smedsrud, L. H., Muilwijk, M., Brakstad, A., Madonna, E., Lauvset, S. K., Spensberger, C., et al. (2022). Nordic seas heat loss, Atlantic inflow, and Arctic Sea Ice cover over the last century. *Reviews of Geophysics*, *60*(1), e2020RG000725. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020RG000725>
- Spall, M. A., Almansi, M., Huang, J., Haine, T. W., & Pickart, R. S. (2021). Lateral redistribution of heat and salt in the Nordic Seas. *Progress in Oceanography*, *196*, 102609. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pocean.2021.102609>
- Speer, K., & Tziperman, E. (1992). Rates of water mass formation in the North Atlantic Ocean. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, *22*(1), 93–104. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0485\(1992\)022<0093:ROWMFI>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0485(1992)022<0093:ROWMFI>2.0.CO;2)
- Spensberger, C., & Spengler, T. (2021). Sensitivity of air–sea heat exchange in cold-air outbreaks to model resolution and sea-ice distribution. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, *126*(5), e2020JD033610. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020JD033610>
- Steele, M., Morley, R., & Ermold, W. (2001). PHC: A global ocean hydrography with a high-quality Arctic Ocean. *Journal of Climate*, *14*(9), 2079–2087. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0442\(2001\)014<2079:PAGOHV>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0442(2001)014<2079:PAGOHV>2.0.CO;2)
- Steffen, E. L., & D'Asaro, E. A. (2002). Deep convection in the Labrador Sea as observed by Lagrangian floats. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, *32*(2), 475–492. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0485\(2002\)032<0475:DCITLS>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0485(2002)032<0475:DCITLS>2.0.CO;2)
- Stevens, B., Satoh, M., Auger, L., Biercamp, J., Bretherton, C., Chen, X., et al. (2019). DYAMOND: The Dynamics of the atmospheric circulation modeled on non-hydrostatic domains. *Progress in Earth and Planetary Science*, *6*(61), 61. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40645-019-0304-z>
- Svingen, K., Brakstad, A., Våge, K., von Appen, W.-J., & Papritz, L. (2023). The impact of cold-air outbreaks and oceanic lateral fluxes on dense-water formation in the Greenland Sea from a 10-year moored record (1999–2009). *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, *53*(6), 1499–1517. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JPO-D-22-01160.1>
- Terpstra, A., Renfrew, I. A., & Sergeev, D. E. (2021). Characteristics of cold-air outbreak events and associated polar mesoscale cyclogenesis over the North Atlantic region. *Journal of Climate*, *34*(11), 4567–4584. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-20-0595.1>
- Tian, T., Yang, S., Høyer, J., Nielsen-Englyst, P., & Singha, S. (2024). Cooler Arctic surface temperatures simulated by climate models are closer to satellite-based data than the ERA5 reanalysis. *Communications Earth & Environment*, *5*(1), 111. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-024-01276-z>
- Tsubouchi, T., Våge, K., Hansen, B., Larsen, K. M. H., Østerhus, S., Johnson, C., et al. (2021). Increased ocean heat transport into the Nordic Seas and Arctic Ocean over the period 1993–2016. *Nature Climate Change*, *11*, 21–26. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-020-00941-3>
- UNESCO. (1981). *The practical salinity scale 1978 and the international equation of state of seawater 1980*. UNESCO. technical papers in marine science 36.
- Våge, K., Moore, G., Jónsson, S., & Valdimarsson, H. (2015). Water mass transformation in the Iceland Sea. *Deep Sea Research Part I: Oceanographic Research Papers*, *101*, 98–109. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dsr.2015.04.001>
- Våge, K., Papritz, L., Håvik, L., Spall, M. A., & Moore, G. (2018). Ocean convection linked to the recent ice edge retreat along east Greenland. *Nature Communications*, *9*(1), 1287. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-03468-6>
- Våge, K., Semper, S., Valdimarsson, H., Jónsson, S., Pickart, R. S., & Moore, G. (2022). Water mass transformation in the Iceland Sea: Contrasting two winters separated by four decades. *Deep Sea Research Part I: Oceanographic Research Papers*, *186*, 103824. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dsr.2022.103824>
- Wang, Q., Danilov, S., Jung, T., Kaleschke, L., & Wernecke, A. (2016). Sea ice leads in the Arctic Ocean: Model assessment, interannual variability and trends. *Geophysical Research Letters*, *43*(13), 7019–7027. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2016GL068696>
- Wu, L. (2021). Effect of atmosphere–wave–ocean/ice interactions on a polar low simulation over the Barents Sea. *Atmospheric Research*, *248*, 105183. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosres.2020.105183>
- Zhou, L., Heuzé, C., & Mohrmann, M. (2023). Sea ice production in the 2016 and 2017 Maud Rise polynyas. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, *128*(2), e2022JC019148. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2022JC019148>
- Zuo, H., Balmaseda, M. A., Tietsche, S., Mogensen, K., & Mayer, M. (2019). The ECMWF operational ensemble reanalysis–analysis system for ocean and sea ice: A description of the system and assessment. *Ocean Science*, *15*(3), 779–808. <https://doi.org/10.5194/os-15-779-2019>